

Project public website

www.esiwace.eu

Deliverable D7.2

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Visit us on: www.esiwace.eu

About this document

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Access our documents in Zenodo:

<https://zenodo.org/communities/esiwace>

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1. Abstract /publishable summary.....	4
2. Conclusion & Results.....	4
3. Project objectives.....	4
4. Detailed report on the deliverable	5
4.1 Structure of the website.....	5
4.2 Who is responsible for the website?	6
4.3 Target audiences	6
5. References (<i>Bibliography</i>).....	6
6. Changes made and/or difficulties encountered, if any	6
8. Sustainability	7
8.2. Links built with other deliverables, WPs, and synergies created with other projects.....	7
8.1. Lessons learnt: both positive and negative that can be drawn from the experiences of the work to date.....	7
9. Dissemination, Engagement and Uptake of Results.....	7

1. Abstract /publishable summary

ESIWACE stands for **Centre of Excellence in Simulation of Weather and Climate in Europe: the community of ESIWACE is made up of two projects, ESIWACE and ESIWACE2**, both funded under the H2020 programme with two different grants.

The website www.esiwace.eu presents the community behind the **Centre of Excellence (CoE)** in its entirety, with information on the goals, expected impacts, project tools and results, providing a global overview on the work plan, the main achievements and the partners.

2. Conclusion & Results

This document is describing the website basic structure. Updates of the website content and of the structure are foreseen during the project lifetime and will be described in the periodic progress reports.

3. Project objectives

This deliverable contributes to the achievement of all the macro-objectives and specific goals indicated in section 1.1 of the Description of the Action.

The website enables the partners to achieve directly and indirectly all the objectives listed below.

The website is a tool, a window to the world for spreading information about the CoE and its results.

Macro-objectives	Contribution of this deliverable?
(1) Enable leading European weather and climate models to leverage the available performance of pre-exascale systems with regard to both compute and data capacity in 2021.	Yes
(2) Prepare the weather and climate community to be able to make use of exascale systems when they become available.	Yes

Specific goals in the workplan	Contribution of this deliverable?
Boost European climate and weather models to operate in world-leading quality on existing supercomputing and future pre-exascale platforms	Yes
Establish new technologies for weather and climate modelling	Yes
Enhance HPC capacity of the weather and climate community	Yes
Improve the toolchain to manage data from climate and weather simulations at scale	Yes
Strengthen the interaction with the European HPC ecosystem	Yes
Foster co-design between model developers, HPC manufacturers and HPC centres	Yes

4. Detailed report on the deliverable

4.1 Structure of the website

The layout as well as the navigation structure and its functional representation are key elements for the website. The users are guided through the navigation and all interactive elements are intuitive to ensure optimal usability. At the same time the visual appearance is up to the state of art, helping new users to orientate themselves and immediately find typical entry points to the content.

Home page

On the home page, a short abstract of the Centre of Excellence, news, upcoming events and a list of tabs are given. It also contains the full acknowledgement of the funding provided by the H2020 programme.

Tab Sections (Sections)

The website contains the following tabs sections: services, trainings, results, overview, events and stay tuned.

Services

Under the sub tab **Software Support** descriptions of specific software packages including support access is given. A short abstract of the **DYAMOND initiative** including application form, news and general contact is presented in a sub tab. Announcements and application for future **HPC user-services**, as will be provided by WP3 of ESIWACE2, are given in an additional sub tab.

Trainings

This section offers a detailed description of future offered trainings to [transfer general knowledge from experts to the community](#), as will be provided by WP6 of ESIWACE2.

Results

In this section we offer the possibility to access the results of the CoE:

- Conference contributions (talks and posters), deliverables, milestones via direct links to the ESIWACE Zenodo community. <https://zenodo.org/communities/esiwace>
- Peer-reviewed articles via links to the OpenAIRE repository for the ESIWACE and ESIWACE2 projects: <https://www.openaire.eu/>

Underneath a show room gives a short insight into best results and success stories.

Overview and Background

This section offers an overview of the strategies of a competitive HPC ecosystem for the European Union. Additional information on the CoE and its goals are presented here, with insights on the two projects of the CoE community with information on the project goals, list of partners and supporters and on the European HPC strategy and the Weather and Climate Computing within the European HPC Strategy.

Events

This page provided information announcements of meetings, workshops, conferences of relevance our community has contributed to.

Stay tuned

In this section, the visitors are invited to follow up on the project activities by registering to the newsletter, following the Twitter account and the news concerning the CoE.

Except for the Overview section, all other sections are meant to be enhanced in the future by updating their content.

4.2 Who is responsible for the website?

Except the Overview section, all sections will grow within the future by updating their content. Contents are provided by all scientists involved in the project to the Project Office (DKRZ) and then transferred to the website.

4.3 Target audiences

Most of the pages of the website target broader audiences, with a plain comprehensible language for non-scientists.

In the sections relate to Results, Services and Trainings the register is more science-oriented, targeting mostly fellow scientists.

5. References (*Bibliography*)

IPR helpdesk brochure "Making the Most of Your H2020 Project. Boosting the impact of your project through effective communication, dissemination and exploitation

https://www.iprhelpdesk.eu/sites/default/files/EU-IPR-Brochure-Boosting-Impact-C-D-E_0.pdf

60-minute workout webinar to increase the communication impact of your project:

<http://www.streamdis.eu/commsworkout2/>

Communicating Your Project: http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/grants/grant-management/communication_en.htm

Guidance Social media guide for EU funded R&I projects Version 1.0 6 April 2018

ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/other/grants_manual/amga/soc-med-guide_en.pdf

6. Changes made and/or difficulties encountered, if any

The challenge for us is to make sure that the CoE is understood in its entirety as community on the website www.esiwace.eu, and that the name ESIWACE2 is the name of one of the funding grants of this community.

7. How this deliverable contributes to the European strategies for HPC

This deliverable is a part of the dissemination and communication activities of the ESIWACE2 project. Beside public information for a broader public, it provides information and contacts for the HPC weather and climate community in order to:

- further explore suitable innovative technologies and software to improve model performance and data in- and output (section Services) and
- transfer general knowledge from ESIWACE experts to the community (section Trainings).

The website allows sharing of knowledge with the community, and enables the community to improve efficiency and productivity of numerical weather and climate simulations and make use of future pre-exascale and exascale systems.

8. Sustainability

8.2. Links built with other deliverables, WPs, and synergies created with other projects

- The access to the intranet (D7.1) is provided through the website: <https://www.esiwace.eu/login>
- Under the section Events we are providing information related to relevant meetings of the HPC Ecosystem in Europe: <https://www.esiwace.eu/events> with information on events organised by other centres of excellence, FET HPC projects, EXDCI, ETP4HPC, PRACE and relevant services at the European Commission.

8.1. Lessons learnt: both positive and negative that can be drawn from the experiences of the work to date

- The website is a living tool for the project. It is the basic tool for providing information about the project and its services and results to large audiences. It is for us strategic that the information presented there stays up to date.
- Instead of publishing documents at the website, links to Zenodo and OpenAIRE are provided. This increases the maintainability of the website by avoiding doubled information.
- For a better understanding of the texts, acronyms are always complemented with their full name and community specific terms are explained.

9. Dissemination, Engagement and Uptake of Results

As indicated in the Description of the Action, the audience for this deliverable is the general public (PU):

This is how we are going to ensure the uptake of the deliverables by the targeted audience:

- Indication of the website is provided in all materials created by the project
- Regular tweets will refer to materials published on the website
- This deliverable will be shared on Zenodo